

Photogalvanic effect and second harmonic generation from radio to infrared region in WTe₂ monolayer

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Second-order nonlinear optical responses, including photogalvanic effect (PGE) and second harmonic generation (SHG), are fundamental and important physical phenomena in nonlinear optics and optoelectronics. The PGE and SHG associated with linearly and circularly polarized light are called the linear photogalvanic effect (LPGE), circular photogalvanic effect (CPGE), linear second harmonic generation (LSHG), and circular second harmonic generation (CSHG), respectively. In this work, we use the quantum kinetics under the relaxation time approximation to investigate the dependence of second-order nonlinear optical responses on Fermi level and frequency under different out-of-plane electric fields in T_d -WTe₂ monolayer from radio to infrared region. We find that the maximum frequency at which the Berry curvature dipole mechanism for the nonlinear Hall effect plays a major role is about 1 THz. From the aspect of Fermi level, in the radio and microwave regions, the two large peaks of nonlinear conductivities occur when the Fermi level is equal to the energy corresponding to the vicinity of the gap-opening points in the band dispersion. From the aspect of frequency, in the radio region, the LPGE and SHG conductivities maintain a large constant while the CPGE conductivity almost disappears. In the microwave region, the LPGE and SHG conductivities start to decrease gradually with increasing frequency while the CPGE conductivity is large. In the infrared region, the frequency and Fermi level dependence of second-order nonlinear optical responses is complicated. In the 125 THz-300 THz region and in the y -direction, the presence of DC current without the disturbance of second harmonic current under circularly polarized light may be useful for the fabrication of new optoelectronic devices. Moreover, we illustrate that when calculating the nonlinear Hall effect or second-order nonlinear optical responses of practical materials, the theories in the clean limit fail and it is necessary to use a theory that takes into account scattering effects (e.g., relaxation time approximation). We also point out that for materials with femtosecond-scale relaxation times and complex energy band structures, the quantum kinetics method is more accurate than the semi-classical Boltzmann equation method. Besides, phenomenological expressions of PGE and SHG are provided. Our study is promising to promote the more accurate calculation of second-order nonlinear optical responses in practical materials.

I. INTRODUCTION

Nonlinear optical phenomena in solids can be used to probe symmetry breaking, new phases of materials as well as quantum geometry and topology¹. Second-order nonlinear optical responses under monochromatic light can be classified as the photogalvanic effect (PGE) and the second harmonic generation (SHG). The PGE, also known as the bulk photovoltaic effect, refers to the generation of DC current when light strikes a homogeneous material that lacks inversion symmetry²⁻⁴. The PGE associated with linearly and circularly polarized light are called linear photogalvanic effect (LPGE) and circular photogalvanic effect (CPGE), respectively^{2,3}. The SHG refers to the generation of **frequency-doubled current and the second harmonic radiated from it** when light or an alternating electric field is applied to a homogeneous material that lacks inversion symmetry⁵⁻⁷. The SHG associated with linearly and circularly polarized light^{8,9} are called linear second harmonic generation (LSHG) and circular second harmonic generation (CSHG), respectively.

The nonlinear Hall effect (NHE) is similar to the low-frequency version of LPGE and LSHG, but it only considers the current transverse to the alternating electric field^{1,10}. The semi-classical Boltzmann equation method reveals that this

transverse current originates from the Berry curvature dipole (BCD)¹⁰, which has been verified by many experiments^{7,11,12}. Recent studies have found that BCD can also be reproduced in quantum kinetics, which also reveals the existence of injection, shift and rectification terms in the PGE besides BCD term¹³⁻¹⁵. Hence it is worth exploring the role of these terms in nonlinear transport for practical materials.

Recently, the WTe₂ monolayer has attracted a lot of attention from experimental and theoretical aspects due to its exotic properties such as quantum spin Hall states^{16,17}, superconductivity¹⁸, NHE¹⁹, CPGE²⁰ and SHG^{21,22}. These studies imply the non-trivial geometrical nature of energy band in the WTe₂ monolayer.

The WTe₂ monolayer has two phases, the $1T'$ phase and the T_d phase, which differ very little²⁰ and can be roughly considered as the same phase²³. The $1T'$ phase has perfect inversion symmetry and the T_d phase weakly breaks the inversion symmetry^{20,22,24}. The T_d -WTe₂ monolayer only has the mirror symmetry \mathcal{M}_y [see the dashed line in Fig. 1(b)] and its point group is C_{1s} , which is actually the symmetry existing in the dual-gated experiments²⁰. When a vertical external electric field is applied by dual gates, the inversion symmetry of the WTe₂ monolayer is more strongly broken and it is induced to produce a net dipole moment, which strongly affects

FIG. 1. (Color online) (a,b,c) The structure of monolayer T_d -WTe₂. (d) The first Brillouin zone of T_d -WTe₂. The coordinates of X, Y, Q and Q' are (0.5, 0), (0, 0.9), (0, 0.385) and (0, -0.385) Å⁻¹, respectively. Q and Q' are the gap-opening points²⁴.

the in-plane transport properties^{20,24}.

The experiment of Ref. 7 has shown that the NHE of T_d -WTe₂ at frequencies below 1000 Hz is contributed by BCD. Therefore, two questions then arise: What is the frequency upper limit below which the BCD mechanism of T_d -WTe₂ monolayer can play a major role? What are the main mechanisms of second-order nonlinear optical responses at higher frequencies? In addition, the dependence of the CPGE of T_d -WTe₂ monolayer on the out-of-plane electric field E_{\perp} at a fixed Fermi level and frequency of 29 THz has been studied in Ref. 20 by mid-infrared optoelectronic microscopy and the theory of injection current in the two-band limit. However, the general dependence of PGE and SHG on frequency and Fermi level remains unclear.

In this paper, we use the quantum kinetics under the relaxation time approximation¹³ to investigate the dependence of PGE and SHG on Fermi level and frequency under different E_{\perp} in T_d -WTe₂ monolayer. The theory shows that second-order nonlinear conductivities can be classified into Drude, BCD, interband 2 (IB2), interband 3 (IB3) terms¹³. When the relaxation time τ is taken as 5 ps, the contribution mechanisms of second-order nonlinear optical responses in T_d -WTe₂ monolayer in different frequency regions are summarized in Table I, which also shows that the maximum frequency at which the BCD mechanism of the nonlinear Hall effect plays a major role is about 1 THz. From the aspect of Fermi level, in the radio and microwave regions, the two large peaks of nonlinear conductivities occur when the Fermi level is equal to the energy corresponding to the vicinity of the gap-opening points in the band dispersion. From the aspect of frequency, in the radio region, the LPGE and SHG conductivities maintain a large constant while the CPGE conductivity almost disappears. In the microwave region, the LPGE and SHG conductivities start to decrease gradually with increasing frequency while the CPGE conductivity is large. In the infrared region, the frequency and Fermi level dependence of second-order nonlinear optical responses is complicated.

In the 125 THz-300 THz region and in the y -direction, the presence of CPGE without the disturbance of CSHG may be useful for the fabrication of new optoelectronic devices (e.g., circularly polarized infrared photodetectors^{25,26} and electromagnetic wave energy harvesting rectifiers²⁷). Moreover, we illustrate that when calculating the NHE or second-order nonlinear optical responses of practical materials, the theories in the clean limit (e.g., Refs. 14, 15, 28, and 29) fail and it is essential to use a theory that takes into account scattering effects (e.g., relaxation time approximation). We also demonstrate that for materials with femtosecond-scale relaxation times and complex energy band structures, the quantum kinetics method is more accurate than the semi-classical Boltzmann equation method.

We also give phenomenological expressions for PGE and SHG. In previous works on PGE^{2-4,15,29,30}, it was only noticed that if the real part of a second-order PGE conductivity expression $\sigma_{(2)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, -\omega)$ is symmetric under the exchange of indices α and β , it relates to linearly polarized light; and if its imaginary part is antisymmetric under the exchange of indices α and β , it relates to circularly polarized light. According to this principle, it can be judged that the shift and injection currents in the clean limit are related to LPGE and CPGE, respectively^{4,29,30}. In addition, the procedure of transforming the conductivity to a new symmetrized expression Eq. (20) was previously used in the early work Ref. 29 in order to facilitate the simplification and analysis of conductivity expressions. In this work, we find a new application of this symmetrization procedure, i.e., for any PGE conductivity expression, we only need to transform it into Eq. (20) and then take the real and imaginary parts of this new expression to obtain the conductivity formulas of LPGE and CPGE. **Unlike PGE, for any SHG conductivity expression, we only need to transform it to Eq. (20) and then take the modulus to obtain the effective LSHG and CSHG conductivities.**

II. QUANTUM KINETICS

Although Matsyshyn and Sodemann¹³ have given nonlinear optical conductivities formulas Eqs. (24)-(27) by using quantum kinetics under the relaxation time approximation, we briefly review these basic formulas in this section for completeness. In addition, in this section, we deeply analyze the properties of these basic formulas and specify the importance of nonzero relaxation rate [see also Subsection E of Section VIII of Supplementary Material (SM)³⁴]. Hereafter we set the alternating electric field as

$$\vec{E}(t) = \sum_i \vec{E}(\omega_i) e^{-i\omega_i t} \equiv \vec{E}(\omega_i) e^{-i\omega_i t}, \quad (1)$$

where ω_i is the angular frequency of the light and the repeated index ω_i indicates summation, e.g., for monochromatic polarized light, $\omega_i = \omega(-\omega)$ as $i = 1(2)$ [see Eq. (28)]. In the ‘‘independent particle approximation’’²⁹, we can set the total

TABLE I. Contribution mechanisms of PGE and SHG in T_d -WTe₂ monolayer in different frequency regions (relaxation time $\tau = 5$ ps). The division of the frequency regions refers to Ref. 31.

	radio region < 0.3 GHz	microwave region 0.3 GHz – 0.3 THz	0.3 THz – 50 THz	infrared region 50 THz – 100 THz	100 THz – 400 THz
Contribution to LPGE	BCD	BCD ^a	None	IB3	None
Contribution to CPGE	None	BCD ^b	None	IB2	IB2
Contribution to LSHG	BCD	BCD	BCD, IB3	BCD, IB3 ^c	None
Contribution to CSHG	BCD	BCD	BCD, IB3	BCD, IB3 ^c	None

^a For LPGE, the frequency range of its contribution can be extended to 1 THz.

^b For CPGE, the frequency range of its contribution can be extended to 5 THz.

^c For SHG, the frequency range of their contribution can be extended to 125 THz.

Hamiltonian of each electron to be H_T :

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{H}_T &= \hat{H}_0 + \hat{H}_E + \hat{U}, \\ \hat{H}_0 &= \frac{\hat{p}^2}{2m} + V(\vec{r}), \\ \hat{H}_E &= e\vec{r} \cdot \vec{E}(t),\end{aligned}\quad (2)$$

where $V(\vec{r})$ is the lattice periodic potential, $e > 0$ is set and $-e$ is for the charge of electron, U is the scattering potential, \hat{H}_E represents the electric potential energy of the electron caused by the alternating electric field.

In the relaxation time approximation, the time evolution equation of the single particle density operator is^{4,13,32,33} (see SM³⁴)

$$i\hbar \frac{d\hat{\rho}}{dt} - [\hat{H}_0 + \hat{H}_E, \hat{\rho}] = -i\hbar\Gamma(\hat{\rho}(t) - \hat{\rho}^e), \quad (3)$$

where the relaxation rate $\Gamma \equiv 1/\tau$, τ is the relaxation time, $\hat{\rho}^e$ is the single-particle density operator at thermodynamic equilibrium. Due to the complexity of the relaxation processes⁴ and the existence of intraband and interband mixing effects, here we use a uniform τ for simplicity, which is a qualitative treatment⁴. We set the Bloch eigenstate of \hat{H}_0 as $|n\vec{k}\rangle$, the eigenenergy as $\varepsilon_n(\vec{k})$ and the periodic part of the Bloch wave $|n\vec{k}\rangle$ as $u_{n\vec{k}}(\vec{r})$. n and \vec{k} are the band index and crystal momentum, respectively. We let $f_n(\vec{k})$ be the Fermi-Dirac distribution function corresponding to the state $|n\vec{k}\rangle$, $f_{mn}(\vec{k}) \equiv f_m(\vec{k}) - f_n(\vec{k})$, $\varepsilon_{mn}(\vec{k}) \equiv \varepsilon_m(\vec{k}) - \varepsilon_n(\vec{k})$. The non-Abelian Berry connection is defined as^{13,35}:

$$\vec{\xi}_{nm}(\vec{k}) = i \int_{N\Omega} u_{n\vec{k}}^* \frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{k}} u_{m\vec{k}} d^3r, \quad (4)$$

where $N\Omega$ is the total crystal volume. Hereafter α, β, η refer to Cartesian component.

By iterating we can perturbatively solve Eq. (3) and obtain the first-order density matrix $\rho_{nm}^{(1)}(t)$ and the second-order density matrix $\rho_{nm}^{(2)}(t)$ (see SM³⁴). The charge current density can be derived by multiplying $\rho_{nm}(t)$ with the velocity operator matrix element $v_{mn}^\eta(\vec{k})$ (see SM³⁴). The discussion of the first-order current density can be seen in SM³⁴. Next we focus on the second-order current density $\langle j_\eta \rangle^{(2)}$. Considering

that τ in the experiments is on the order of picoseconds³⁶ or femtoseconds^{7,12,20,37}, we can set

$$\langle j_\eta \rangle^{(2)} \equiv \sigma_{(2)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega_i, \omega_j) E_\alpha(\omega_i) E_\beta(\omega_j) e^{-i(\omega_i + \omega_j)t}, \quad (5)$$

where repeated indices $\omega_i, \omega_j, \alpha$ and β indicate summation²⁹. We can obtain

$$\begin{aligned}\langle j_\eta \rangle^{(2)} &\equiv \left[\sigma_{(2)(i)(ii)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega_i, \omega_j) + \sigma_{(2)(e)(ie)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega_i, \omega_j) \right. \\ &\quad + \sigma_{(2)(e)(ei)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega_i, \omega_j) + \sigma_{(2)(i)(ee)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega_i, \omega_j) \\ &\quad \left. + \sigma_{(2)(e)(ee)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega_i, \omega_j) \right] E_\alpha(\omega_i) E_\beta(\omega_j) e^{-i(\omega_i + \omega_j)t},\end{aligned}\quad (6)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_{(2)(i)(ii)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega_i, \omega_j) &= \frac{e^3}{\hbar^3} \int \frac{d^3k}{(2\pi)^3} \sum_n d^{\omega_i} d^{\omega_i + \omega_j} (\partial_{k_\eta} \varepsilon_n) \partial_{k_\alpha} \partial_{k_\beta} f_n(\vec{k}),\end{aligned}\quad (7)$$

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_{(2)(e)(ei)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega_i, \omega_j) &= \frac{e^3}{\hbar^3} \int \frac{d^3k}{(2\pi)^3} \sum_{nm} d^{\omega_i} d^{\omega_i + \omega_j} \varepsilon_{mn} \xi_{mn}^\eta \xi_{nm}^\beta \partial_{k_\alpha} f_{mn}(\vec{k}),\end{aligned}\quad (8)$$

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_{(2)(e)(ie)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega_i, \omega_j) &= \frac{e^3}{\hbar^3} \int \frac{d^3k}{(2\pi)^3} \sum_{nm} \left\{ d_{nm}^{\omega_i + \omega_j} \varepsilon_{mn} \xi_{mn}^\eta \xi_{nm}^\alpha \partial_{k_\beta} [d_{nm}^{\omega_i} f_{mn}(\vec{k})] \right. \\ &\quad \left. + d_{nm}^{\omega_i} d_{nm}^{\omega_i + \omega_j} \varepsilon_{mn} f_{mn} \xi_{mn}^\eta \xi_{nm;\beta}^\alpha \right\},\end{aligned}\quad (9)$$

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_{(2)(i)(ee)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega_i, \omega_j) &= -\frac{e^3}{\hbar^3} \int \frac{d^3k}{(2\pi)^3} \sum_{nm} \hbar d^{\omega_i + \omega_j} d_{nm}^{\omega_i} f_{nm} \Delta_{nm}^\eta \xi_{nm}^\alpha \xi_{mn}^\beta,\end{aligned}\quad (10)$$

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_{(2)(e)(ee)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega_i, \omega_j) &= -\frac{e^3}{\hbar^3} \int \frac{d^3k}{(2\pi)^3} \sum_{nm} [i d_{nm}^{\omega_i + \omega_j} \varepsilon_{mn} \xi_{mn}^\eta \\ &\quad \times \sum_{l \neq n, m} (d_{lm}^{\omega_i} \xi_{lm}^\alpha \xi_{nl}^\beta f_{ml} - d_{nl}^{\omega_i} \xi_{nl}^\alpha \xi_{lm}^\beta f_{ln})],\end{aligned}\quad (11)$$

$$d_{nm}^{\omega} \equiv \frac{1}{\omega - \varepsilon_{nm}/\hbar + i\Gamma}, \quad (12)$$

$$d^{\omega} \equiv \frac{1}{\omega + i\Gamma}, \quad (13)$$

$$\Delta_{nm}^{\alpha} \equiv v_{nn}^{\alpha} - v_{mm}^{\alpha} = \frac{1}{\hbar} \frac{\partial \varepsilon_{nm}}{\partial k_{\alpha}}, \quad (14)$$

and the ‘‘generalized derivatives’’ of $\vec{\xi}_{nm}$ is defined by²⁹

$$\xi_{nm;\alpha}^{\beta} \equiv \partial_{k_{\alpha}} \xi_{nm}^{\beta} - i(\xi_{nn}^{\alpha} - \xi_{mm}^{\alpha}) \xi_{nm}^{\beta}. \quad (15)$$

The subscripts ‘‘*i*’’ and ‘‘*e*’’ in Eq. (6) denote intraband and interband, respectively. Our classification of intraband and interband effects is based on how many times the intraband position operator \hat{r}_i and interband position operator \hat{r}_e are used in the derivation^{14,28,29,34}. ‘‘(i)(ii)’’ in Eq. (7) indicates that this term comes from the product of intraband velocity operator matrix element $v_{mn}^{(i)\eta}$ and intraband second-order density matrix $\rho_{nm}^{(2)(ii)}$. ‘‘(e)(ie)’’ in Eq. (9) indicates that this term comes from the product of interband velocity operator matrix element $v_{mn}^{(e)\eta}$ and intraband-interband mixing second-order density matrix $\rho_{nm}^{(2)(ie)}$, and so on for other terms. Hence $\sigma_{(2)(i)(ii)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}$ is a pure intraband term and is also called the Drude term^{14,15}. $\sigma_{(2)(e)(ee)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}$ is a pure interband term, while the other second-order conductivity terms mix intraband and interband effects. Eqs. (7)-(11) correspond to Eqs. (25)-(28) of Ref. 14, which have set $\Gamma = 0^+$ but here we do not and we give a more complete analysis of the intraband and interband effects.

Now we discuss $\sigma_{(2)(e)(ei)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}$. When $\omega_i + \omega_j \ll |\varepsilon_{nm}/\hbar|$ ¹³ and $\Gamma \ll |\varepsilon_{nm}/\hbar|$, making use of

$$\frac{\varepsilon_{mn}}{\omega_i + \omega_j - \varepsilon_{nm}/\hbar + i\Gamma} \approx \frac{\varepsilon_{mn}}{\varepsilon_{mn}/\hbar + i\Gamma} \approx \hbar, \quad (16)$$

and the definition of Berry curvature

$$\Omega_n^{\alpha\eta} \equiv \frac{\partial}{\partial k_{\alpha}} \xi_{nn}^{\eta} - \frac{\partial}{\partial k_{\eta}} \xi_{nn}^{\alpha}, \quad (17)$$

$$\Omega_n^z \equiv \frac{\partial}{\partial k_x} \xi_{nn}^y - \frac{\partial}{\partial k_y} \xi_{nn}^x = \Omega_n^{xy} = -\Omega_n^{yx},$$

Eq. (8) can be reduced to the form of the Berry curvature dipole¹³:

$$\sigma_{(2)(e)(ei)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega_i, \omega_j) = \frac{e^3}{\hbar^2} \frac{i}{\omega_i + i\Gamma} \int \frac{d^3k}{(2\pi)^3} \sum_n f_n(\vec{k}) \partial_{k_{\alpha}} \Omega_n^{\eta\beta}, \quad (18)$$

so $\sigma_{(2)(e)(ei)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega_i, \omega_j)$ is also called the BCD or ‘‘interband 1’’ term¹³. For PGE, if $\Gamma \ll |\varepsilon_{nm}/\hbar|$ holds, Eq. (8) can reduce to the traditional BCD formula Eq. (18) for light of any frequency. For SHG, Eq. (18) holds only if both the low frequencies ($2\omega \ll |\varepsilon_{nm}/\hbar|$) and $\Gamma \ll |\varepsilon_{nm}/\hbar|$ are satisfied. However, when the relaxation time is taken as 5 ps³⁶ and 10 fs^{7,12,20,37}, $\hbar\Gamma$ is 0.13 meV and 65.82 meV, respectively, which

do not satisfy $\Gamma \ll |\varepsilon_{nm}/\hbar|$ for the T_d -WTe₂ monolayer. For example, when the out-of-plane electric field is 0.2 V/nm, the maximum splitting value between the two lowest conduction bands near the gap-opening points is 26.1 meV²⁰. Thus we still use Eq. (25) instead of Eq. (18) to do the numerical calculation.

Next we discuss $\sigma_{(2)(i)(ee)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}$. From Eq. (5) we know that²⁹

$$\begin{aligned} \langle j_{\eta} \rangle^{(2)} &= \sum_{\alpha\beta} \sum_{\omega_i \omega_j} \sigma_{(2)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega_i, \omega_j) E^{\alpha}(\omega_i) E^{\beta}(\omega_j) e^{-i(\omega_i + \omega_j)t} \\ &= \sum_{\beta\alpha} \sum_{\omega_j \omega_i} \sigma_{(2)}^{\eta\beta\alpha}(\omega_j, \omega_i) E^{\beta}(\omega_j) E^{\alpha}(\omega_i) e^{-i(\omega_i + \omega_j)t} \\ &= \sum_{\alpha\beta} \sum_{\omega_i \omega_j} \left[\frac{1}{2} \sigma_{(2)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega_i, \omega_j) + \frac{1}{2} \sigma_{(2)}^{\eta\beta\alpha}(\omega_j, \omega_i) \right] \\ &\quad \times E^{\alpha}(\omega_i) E^{\beta}(\omega_j) e^{-i(\omega_i + \omega_j)t}. \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Note that we cannot conclude from Eq. (19) that $\sigma_{(2)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega_i, \omega_j) = \sigma_{(2)}^{\eta\beta\alpha}(\omega_j, \omega_i)$ (see SM³⁴). However, if we define a new symmetrized second-order conductivity

$$\sigma_{(2)\text{new}}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega_i, \omega_j) = \frac{1}{2} \sigma_{(2)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega_i, \omega_j) + \frac{1}{2} \sigma_{(2)}^{\eta\beta\alpha}(\omega_j, \omega_i), \quad (20)$$

then

$$\sigma_{(2)\text{new}}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega_i, \omega_j) = \sigma_{(2)\text{new}}^{\eta\beta\alpha}(\omega_j, \omega_i). \quad (21)$$

Thus we can use Eq. (20) to obtain another expression of $\sigma_{(2)(i)(ee)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega_i, \omega_j)$ ¹⁵ (see SM³⁴)

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{(2)(i)(ee)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega_i, \omega_j) &= \frac{-e^3}{\hbar^3} \int \frac{d^3k}{(2\pi)^3} \sum_{nm} \hbar d^{\omega_i + \omega_j} d_{nm}^{\omega_i} f_{nm} \Delta_{nm}^{\eta} \xi_{nm}^{\alpha} \xi_{nm}^{\beta} \\ &\quad + [(\alpha, \omega_i) \leftrightarrow (\beta, \omega_j)] \\ &= \frac{-e^3}{2\hbar^3} \int \frac{d^3k}{8\pi^3} \sum_{nm} \hbar d^{\omega_i + \omega_j} (d_{nm}^{\omega_i} + d_{mn}^{\omega_j}) f_{nm} \Delta_{nm}^{\eta} \xi_{nm}^{\beta} \xi_{nm}^{\alpha}. \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

In the case of PGE and the clean limit ($\Gamma \rightarrow 0^+$), Eq. (22) can be reduced to a formula containing the expression of the injection current in Ref. 29^{14,15}. Therefore Eq. (22) can also be called the ‘‘injection’’ or ‘‘interband 2 (IB2)’’ term under the relaxation time approximation (Γ is finite)¹³.

Finally we discuss $\sigma_{(2)(e)(ie)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}$ and $\sigma_{(2)(e)(ee)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}$. In the case of PGE and the clean limit ($\Gamma \rightarrow 0^+$), $\sigma_{(2)(e)(ie)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega_i, \omega_j) + \sigma_{(2)(e)(ee)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega_i, \omega_j)$ can be reduced to a formula containing the expression of the shift current in Ref. 29^{14,15}. Therefore $\sigma_{(2)(e)(ie)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega_i, \omega_j) + \sigma_{(2)(e)(ee)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega_i, \omega_j)$ can also be called the ‘‘shift’’ or ‘‘interband 3 (IB3)’’ term under the relaxation time approximation¹³.

In summary, the second-order conductivity under the relaxation time approximation is¹³

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{(2)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega_i, \omega_j) &= \sigma_{(2)\text{Drude}}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega_i, \omega_j) + \sigma_{(2)\text{BCD}}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega_i, \omega_j) \\ &\quad + \sigma_{(2)\text{IB2}}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega_i, \omega_j) + \sigma_{(2)\text{IB3}}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega_i, \omega_j), \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

where

$$\sigma_{(2)\text{Drude}}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega_i, \omega_j) = \frac{e^3}{2\hbar^3} \int \frac{d^3k}{(2\pi)^3} \sum_n d^{\omega_i} d^{\omega_i+\omega_j} (\partial_{k_\eta} \varepsilon_n) \partial_{k_\alpha} \partial_{k_\beta} f_n(\vec{k}) + [(\alpha, \omega_i) \leftrightarrow (\beta, \omega_j)], \quad (24)$$

$$\sigma_{(2)\text{BCD}}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega_i, \omega_j) = \frac{e^3}{2\hbar^3} \int \frac{d^3k}{(2\pi)^3} \sum_{nm} d^{\omega_i} d^{\omega_i+\omega_j} \varepsilon_{mn} \xi_{mn}^\eta \xi_{nm}^\beta \partial_{k_\alpha} f_{nm}(\vec{k}) + [(\alpha, \omega_i) \leftrightarrow (\beta, \omega_j)], \quad (25)$$

$$\sigma_{(2)\text{IB2}}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega_i, \omega_j) = -\frac{e^3}{4\hbar^3} \int \frac{d^3k}{8\pi^3} \sum_{nm} \hbar d^{\omega_i+\omega_j} (d_{nm}^{\omega_i} + d_{mn}^{\omega_j}) f_{nm} \Delta_{nm}^\eta \xi_{mn}^\beta \xi_{nm}^\alpha + [(\alpha, \omega_i) \leftrightarrow (\beta, \omega_j)], \quad (26)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{(2)\text{IB3}}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega_i, \omega_j) = & \frac{e^3}{2\hbar^3} \int \frac{d^3k}{(2\pi)^3} \sum_{nm} \left\{ d_{nm}^{\omega_i+\omega_j} \varepsilon_{mn} \xi_{mn}^\eta \xi_{nm}^\alpha \partial_{k_\beta} [d_{nm}^{\omega_i} f_{mn}(\vec{k})] + d_{nm}^{\omega_i} d_{nm}^{\omega_i+\omega_j} \varepsilon_{mn} f_{mn} \xi_{mn}^\eta \xi_{nm;\beta}^\alpha \right. \\ & \left. - i d_{nm}^{\omega_i+\omega_j} \varepsilon_{mn} \xi_{mn}^\eta \sum_{l \neq n, m} \left(d_{lm}^{\omega_i} \xi_{lm}^\alpha \xi_{nl}^\beta f_{ml} - d_{nl}^{\omega_i} \xi_{nl}^\alpha \xi_{lm}^\beta f_{ln} \right) \right\} + [(\alpha, \omega_i) \leftrightarrow (\beta, \omega_j)], \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

which are all new second-order conductivities obtained from Eq. (20). And we do not explicitly write the subscript ‘‘new’’ for brevity. It can be proved that when the system has time-reversal symmetry, only the Drude term vanishes and all other terms still exist (see SM³⁴). In the Section V of SM³⁴, using the phenomenological expressions for PGE in Section III, we obtain the universal frequency dependence of the BCD term for the LPGE and CPGE cases as $\text{Re}(\sigma_{(2)\text{BCD}}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, -\omega)) \propto 1/(\omega^2 + \Gamma^2)$ and $\text{Im}(\sigma_{(2)\text{BCD}}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, -\omega)) \propto \omega/(\omega^2 + \Gamma^2)$, respectively. In the case of PGE and the system with time-reversal symmetry, we combine the phenomenological expressions to obtain the reduced expressions for the BCD and IB2 terms, and also find that the LPGE current induced by the BCD term exists only in the direction transverse to the alternating electric field; we also point out that the IB2 term exists only under circularly polarized light and introduce the physical meaning of IB2 term, i.e., when Γ is not reasonably small, the ‘‘injection’’ phenomenon will disappear due to the scattering effect and the injection current will saturate to the IB2 term^{14,38,39}. However, the IB3 term is too complicated and it needs further study in the future. Note that in the case of 2D materials, $d^3k/(2\pi)^3$ should be changed to $d^2k/(2\pi)^2$.

There is a lot of literature discussing the second-order nonlinear optical responses in the clean limit case^{14,15,28,29}. But in practical experiments, the effect of scattering on nonlinear optical responses is important^{4,29,40,41}, and the relaxation time measured in many optical and transport experiments are on the order of picoseconds or femtoseconds^{4,36,37,42}. For a comparison with experiments, we have to take into account the relaxation time and go beyond the clean limit, because these results use $\frac{\varepsilon_{mn}/\hbar}{\varepsilon_{mn}/\hbar+i0^+} \approx 1$ and the Sokhotski-Plemelj Formula $\frac{1}{\omega - \varepsilon_{nm}/\hbar + i0^+} = P \frac{1}{\omega - \varepsilon_{nm}/\hbar} - i\pi\delta(\omega - \varepsilon_{nm}/\hbar)$ ^{14,15,29} (this

formula holds only when $|\omega - \varepsilon_{nm}/\hbar| \gg \Gamma$), which do not hold when Γ is on the order of 10^{11} Hz³⁶ or 10^{14} Hz^{7,12,20,37}. In contrast, in this work, the advantage of second-order conductivity Eq. (23) is that it can be used to handle a variety of situations such as arbitrary and finite relaxation rate Γ (the premise is that the degree of disorder does not render the relaxation time approximation and band theory invalid), PGE and SHG.

For insulators, $\partial_{\vec{k}} f_n(\vec{k})$ vanishes because the Fermi energy is in the band gap and the Fermi surface disappears. Therefore, Drude and the BCD terms do not exist in insulators^{15,28}. In addition, the existence of $\partial_{\vec{k}} f_n(\vec{k})$ also means that the Drude and BCD terms are inherent in the effect of Fermi surface.

III. PHENOMENOLOGICAL EXPRESSION OF PHOTOGALVANIC EFFECT

In this section, we improve the existing theory^{2,3} of phenomenological expressions for PGE [see the discussion below Eq. (38)]. Consider a monochromatic polarized light incident along the normal to a 2D material interface with $z = 0$ in the xy plane. Any kind of polarized light propagating along the z direction can be expressed as the superposition of two linearly polarized lights with electric field vectors along the x -axis and y -axis, respectively⁴³. Thus the electric field at $z = 0$ is⁴³

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{E}(t) &= a_x \cos(\phi_x - \omega t) \vec{e}_x + a_y \cos(\phi_y - \omega t) \vec{e}_y \\ &\equiv \vec{E}(\omega) e^{-i\omega t} + \vec{E}(-\omega) e^{i\omega t}, \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

where the amplitudes a_x, a_y are real numbers, ϕ_x, ϕ_y are the initial phases of the x -direction and the y -direction electric

fields at $z = 0$, respectively. $\vec{E}(\omega)$ and $\vec{E}(-\omega)$ are the complex amplitudes of the electric field, whose expressions can be seen in SM³⁴, and they satisfy¹⁴

$$\vec{E}(\omega) = \vec{E}^*(-\omega). \quad (29)$$

We set $\delta \equiv \phi_y - \phi_x$ as the initial phase difference. $E_0 = \sqrt{a_x^2 + a_y^2}$ is the amplitude of the electric field $\vec{E}(t)$.

In the following discussion, the precondition is the new second-order conductivity Eq. (20), otherwise we would not be able to derive the following phenomenological expression. For convenience, we will no longer explicitly write the subscript ‘‘new’’ in the following content.

The photocurrents can be described phenomenologically as an expansion in powers of the incident electric field^{2,3}, so the lowest order DC current density can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \langle j_\eta \rangle_{0\omega}^{(2)} &= \sum_{\alpha\beta} \sigma_{(2)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, -\omega) E_\alpha(\omega) E_\beta(-\omega) \\ &+ \sum_{\alpha\beta} \sigma_{(2)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(-\omega, \omega) E_\alpha(-\omega) E_\beta(\omega), \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

which can also be known from Eq. (5). Because $\langle j_\eta \rangle_{0\omega}^{(2)}$ is a real number², one has (see SM³⁴):

$$\sigma_{(2)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(-\omega, \omega) = \left[\sigma_{(2)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, -\omega) \right]^*, \quad (31)$$

where $\alpha = x, y$ and $\beta = x, y$. Eqs. (21) and (31) can be combined to give the relation:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{(2)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(-\omega, \omega) &= \left[\sigma_{(2)}^{\eta\beta\alpha}(-\omega, \omega) \right]^*, \\ \sigma_{(2)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, -\omega) &= \left[\sigma_{(2)}^{\eta\beta\alpha}(\omega, -\omega) \right]^*. \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

We define³⁰

$$\sigma_{(2)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, -\omega) \equiv \sigma_{(2)\text{Re}}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, -\omega) + i\sigma_{(2)\text{Im}}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, -\omega), \quad (33)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{(2)\text{Re}}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, -\omega) &\equiv \text{Re} \left[\sigma_{(2)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, -\omega) \right], \\ \sigma_{(2)\text{Im}}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, -\omega) &\equiv \text{Im} \left[\sigma_{(2)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, -\omega) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

Eqs. (33) and (32) can be combined to give the relation:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{(2)\text{Re}}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, -\omega) &= \sigma_{(2)\text{Re}}^{\eta\beta\alpha}(\omega, -\omega), \\ \sigma_{(2)\text{Im}}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, -\omega) &= -\sigma_{(2)\text{Im}}^{\eta\beta\alpha}(\omega, -\omega), \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

i.e., the real and imaginary parts of $\sigma_{(2)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, -\omega)$ are symmetric and anti-symmetric for the exchange of α and β , respectively.

Any tensor that is antisymmetric about a pair of indices can be expressed as the product of a low-order tensor and the Levi-Civita totally antisymmetric pseudotensor $\varepsilon_{\gamma\alpha\beta}$ ^{2,3}, hence

$$\sigma_{(2)\text{Im}}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, -\omega) \equiv \kappa^{\eta\gamma}(\omega, -\omega) \varepsilon_{\gamma\alpha\beta}, \quad (36)$$

where $\kappa^{\eta\gamma}(\omega, -\omega)$ is a real second-order tensor, γ refers to Cartesian component. We are able to use Eq. (36) to obtain the expression of $\kappa^{\eta\gamma}(\omega, -\omega)$:

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa^{\eta x}(\omega, -\omega) &= \sigma_{(2)\text{Im}}^{\eta y z}(\omega, -\omega), \\ \kappa^{\eta y}(\omega, -\omega) &= \sigma_{(2)\text{Im}}^{\eta z x}(\omega, -\omega), \\ \kappa^{\eta z}(\omega, -\omega) &= \sigma_{(2)\text{Im}}^{\eta x y}(\omega, -\omega), \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

where $\eta = x, y, z$.

Making use of Eqs. (21), (29), (30), (35), (36), we obtain the phenomenological expression of current density for PGE

$$\begin{aligned} \langle j_\eta \rangle_{0\omega}^{(2)} &= 2 \sum_{\alpha\beta} \sigma_{(2)\text{Re}}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, -\omega) \text{Re}(E_\alpha(\omega) E_\beta(-\omega)) \\ &+ 2 \sum_{\gamma} \kappa^{\eta\gamma}(\omega, -\omega) i(\vec{E}(\omega) \times \vec{E}(-\omega))_\gamma. \end{aligned} \quad (38)$$

The difference between Eq. (38) and the phenomenological expression of the PGE current in Refs. 2 and 3 [see Eq. (1.9) of Ref. 2 and Eq. (7.5) of Ref. 3] is the pre-factor 2 in Eq. (38). The reason for this difference is that the theory of Refs. 2 and 3 does not take into account that the repeated frequency index should also be summed when calculating the current density [see Eq. (5)], so the new second-order conductivity formula Eq. (20) is also not considered.

For linearly (L) polarized light, the second line of Eq. (38) vanishes, Eq. (38) reduces to

$$\begin{aligned} \langle j_\eta \rangle_{0\omega}^{(2)(L)} &= \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \sigma_{(2)\text{Re}}^{\eta x x}(\omega, -\omega) a_x^2 + \sigma_{(2)\text{Re}}^{\eta y y}(\omega, -\omega) a_y^2 \right. \\ &\left. + \left[\sigma_{(2)\text{Re}}^{\eta x y}(\omega, -\omega) + \sigma_{(2)\text{Re}}^{\eta y x}(\omega, -\omega) \right] a_x a_y \cos \delta \right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

where $\cos \delta = \pm 1$. Only the real part of $\sigma_{(2)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, -\omega)$ contributes to $\langle j_\eta \rangle_{0\omega}^{(2)(L)2,3}$.

For left-handed and right-handed circularly (LC and RC) polarized light, Eq. (38) reduces to

$$\begin{aligned} \langle j_\eta \rangle_{0\omega}^{(2)(LC)} &= \frac{1}{4} E_0^2 \left[\sigma_{(2)\text{Re}}^{\eta x x}(\omega, -\omega) \right. \\ &\left. + \sigma_{(2)\text{Re}}^{\eta y y}(\omega, -\omega) + 2\sigma_{(2)\text{Im}}^{\eta x y}(\omega, -\omega) \right], \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \langle j_\eta \rangle_{0\omega}^{(2)(RC)} &= \frac{1}{4} E_0^2 \left[\sigma_{(2)\text{Re}}^{\eta x x}(\omega, -\omega) \right. \\ &\left. + \sigma_{(2)\text{Re}}^{\eta y y}(\omega, -\omega) - 2\sigma_{(2)\text{Im}}^{\eta x y}(\omega, -\omega) \right], \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

where E_0^2 represents the intensity of monochromatic polarized light⁴³. Although both $\sigma_{(2)\text{Re}}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, -\omega)$ and $\sigma_{(2)\text{Im}}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, -\omega)$ contribute to $\langle j_\eta \rangle_{0\omega}^{(2)(LC)}$ and $\langle j_\eta \rangle_{0\omega}^{(2)(RC)}$, the current difference between $\langle j_\eta \rangle_{0\omega}^{(2)(LC)}$ and $\langle j_\eta \rangle_{0\omega}^{(2)(RC)}$ ³⁰ is

$$\begin{aligned} \langle j_\eta \rangle_{0\omega}^{(2)(CPGE)} &\equiv \langle j_\eta \rangle_{0\omega}^{(2)(LC)} - \langle j_\eta \rangle_{0\omega}^{(2)(RC)} \\ &= \sigma_{(2)\text{Im}}^{\eta x y}(\omega, -\omega) E_0^2, \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

where we have defined $\langle j_\eta \rangle_{0\omega}^{(2)(CPGE)}$ as the response of CPGE²⁰. Only the imaginary part of $\sigma_{(2)}^{\eta x y}(\omega, -\omega)$ contributes

to $\langle j_\eta \rangle_{0\omega}^{(2)(\text{CPGE})}$, i.e., only the second line of Eq. (38) contributes to $\langle j_\eta \rangle_{0\omega}^{(2)(\text{CPGE})}$ ^{2,3,44}.

The above content is phenomenological, however Eqs. (24)-(27) are obtained by the quantum kinetics method, so we need to verify whether they satisfy the phenomenological relation Eq. (31), and in SM³⁴ we prove that they do. Therefore, we can directly take the real and imaginary parts of Eqs. (24)-(27) in the case of PGE to obtain the LPGE and CPGE conductivities.

IV. PHENOMENOLOGICAL EXPRESSIONS OF SECOND HARMONIC GENERATION

In this section, we present a phenomenological analysis for LSHG and CSHG. In the following discussion, the precondition is also the new second-order conductivity Eq. (20). Phenomenologically, the lowest order second harmonic current density can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \langle j_\eta \rangle_{2\omega}^{(2)} &= \sum_{\alpha\beta} \sigma_{(2)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, \omega) E_\alpha(\omega) E_\beta(\omega) e^{-2i\omega t} \\ &+ \sum_{\alpha\beta} \sigma_{(2)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(-\omega, -\omega) E_\alpha(-\omega) E_\beta(-\omega) e^{2i\omega t}, \end{aligned} \quad (43)$$

which can also be known from Eq. (5). From the fact that $\langle j_\eta \rangle_{2\omega}^{(2)}$ is a real number² and Eq. (29), one has the relation (see SM³⁴):

$$\sigma_{(2)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, \omega) = \left[\sigma_{(2)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(-\omega, -\omega) \right]^*, \quad (44)$$

where $\alpha = x, y$ and $\beta = x, y$. Eqs. (21) and (44) can be combined to give relation:

$$\sigma_{(2)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, \omega) = \left[\sigma_{(2)}^{\eta\beta\alpha}(-\omega, -\omega) \right]^*. \quad (45)$$

We define

$$\sigma_{(2)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, \omega) \equiv \sigma_{(2)\text{Re}}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, \omega) + i\sigma_{(2)\text{Im}}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, \omega), \quad (46)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{(2)\text{Re}}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, \omega) &\equiv \text{Re} \left[\sigma_{(2)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, \omega) \right], \\ \sigma_{(2)\text{Im}}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, \omega) &\equiv \text{Im} \left[\sigma_{(2)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, \omega) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (47)$$

Eqs. (46) and (21) can be combined to give the relation:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{(2)\text{Re}}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, \omega) &= \sigma_{(2)\text{Re}}^{\eta\beta\alpha}(\omega, \omega), \\ \sigma_{(2)\text{Im}}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, \omega) &= \sigma_{(2)\text{Im}}^{\eta\beta\alpha}(\omega, \omega), \end{aligned} \quad (48)$$

i.e., the real and imaginary parts of $\sigma_{(2)}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, \omega)$ are all symmetric for the exchange of α and β .

One can also easily verify that Eqs. (24)-(27) satisfy the phenomenological relation Eq. (44).

Eqs. (43) and (44) lead to the phenomenological expression for the current density of the SHG under normal incidence (see SM³⁴):

$$\begin{aligned} \langle j_\eta \rangle_{2\omega}^{(2)} &= \frac{1}{2} a_x a_y \cos(\phi_x + \phi_y) \left[\sigma_{(2)\text{Re}}^{\eta xy}(\omega, \omega) \cos(2\omega t) + \sigma_{(2)\text{Im}}^{\eta xy}(\omega, \omega) \sin(2\omega t) \right] \\ &+ \frac{1}{2} a_x a_y \sin(\phi_x + \phi_y) \left[\sigma_{(2)\text{Re}}^{\eta xy}(\omega, \omega) \sin(2\omega t) - \sigma_{(2)\text{Im}}^{\eta xy}(\omega, \omega) \cos(2\omega t) \right] \\ &+ \frac{1}{4} a_x^2 \cos(2\phi_x) \left[\sigma_{(2)\text{Re}}^{\eta xx}(\omega, \omega) \cos(2\omega t) + \sigma_{(2)\text{Im}}^{\eta xx}(\omega, \omega) \sin(2\omega t) \right] \\ &+ \frac{1}{4} a_x^2 \sin(2\phi_x) \left[\sigma_{(2)\text{Re}}^{\eta xx}(\omega, \omega) \sin(2\omega t) - \sigma_{(2)\text{Im}}^{\eta xx}(\omega, \omega) \cos(2\omega t) \right] \\ &+ \frac{1}{4} a_y^2 \cos(2\phi_y) \left[\sigma_{(2)\text{Re}}^{\eta yy}(\omega, \omega) \cos(2\omega t) + \sigma_{(2)\text{Im}}^{\eta yy}(\omega, \omega) \sin(2\omega t) \right] \\ &+ \frac{1}{4} a_y^2 \sin(2\phi_y) \left[\sigma_{(2)\text{Re}}^{\eta yy}(\omega, \omega) \sin(2\omega t) - \sigma_{(2)\text{Im}}^{\eta yy}(\omega, \omega) \cos(2\omega t) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (49)$$

For linearly polarized light, if we assume that the alternating electric field is along the y direction, Eq. (49) reduces to

$$\langle j_\eta \rangle_{2\omega}^{(2)(\text{L})} = \sigma_{(2)\text{eff}}^{\eta yy}(\omega, \omega) E_0^2 \sin(2\omega t + \varphi_1), \quad (50)$$

where $E_0^2 = a_y^2$ is the intensity of light, $\tan \varphi_1 \equiv \frac{\cos(2\phi_x) \sigma_{(2)\text{Re}}^{\eta yy}(\omega, \omega) - \sin(2\phi_x) \sigma_{(2)\text{Im}}^{\eta yy}(\omega, \omega)}{\cos(2\phi_x) \sigma_{(2)\text{Im}}^{\eta yy}(\omega, \omega) + \sin(2\phi_x) \sigma_{(2)\text{Re}}^{\eta yy}(\omega, \omega)}$ and we define the effective

LSHG conductivity as

$$\sigma_{(2)\text{eff}}^{\eta yy}(\omega, \omega) \equiv \frac{1}{4} \sqrt{\left(\sigma_{(2)\text{Re}}^{\eta yy}(\omega, \omega) \right)^2 + \left(\sigma_{(2)\text{Im}}^{\eta yy}(\omega, \omega) \right)^2}. \quad (51)$$

We can see that the amplitude of the second harmonic current is independent of the initial phase ϕ_x .

For left-handed and right-handed circularly polarized light,

FIG. 2. (a,b,c) Band structures of monolayer T_d -WTe₂ with (a) $E_{\perp} = 0.2$ V/nm, (b) $E_{\perp} = 0.5$ V/nm and (c) $E_{\perp} = 1$ V/nm obtained by using the six-band model. Q and Q' are the gap-opening points.

the current difference between $\langle j_{\eta} \rangle_{2\omega}^{(2)(\text{LC})}$ and $\langle j_{\eta} \rangle_{2\omega}^{(2)(\text{RC})}$ is

$$\begin{aligned} \langle j_{\eta} \rangle_{2\omega}^{(2)(\text{CSHG})} &\equiv \langle j_{\eta} \rangle_{2\omega}^{(2)(\text{LC})} - \langle j_{\eta} \rangle_{2\omega}^{(2)(\text{RC})} \\ &= \sigma_{(2)\text{eff}}^{\eta xy}(\omega, \omega) E_0^2 \sin(2\omega t + \varphi_2), \end{aligned} \quad (52)$$

where we have defined $\langle j_{\eta} \rangle_{2\omega}^{(2)(\text{CSHG})}$ as the response of CSHG, $\tan \varphi_2 \equiv \frac{\sin(2\phi_x) \sigma_{(2)\text{Re}}^{\eta xy}(\omega, \omega) + \cos(2\phi_x) \sigma_{(2)\text{Im}}^{\eta xy}(\omega, \omega)}{\sin(2\phi_x) \sigma_{(2)\text{Im}}^{\eta xy}(\omega, \omega) - \cos(2\phi_x) \sigma_{(2)\text{Re}}^{\eta xy}(\omega, \omega)}$ and we define the effective CSHG conductivity as

$$\sigma_{(2)\text{eff}}^{\eta xy}(\omega, \omega) \equiv \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\left(\sigma_{(2)\text{Re}}^{\eta xy}(\omega, \omega) \right)^2 + \left(\sigma_{(2)\text{Im}}^{\eta xy}(\omega, \omega) \right)^2}. \quad (53)$$

The amplitude of $\langle j_{\eta} \rangle_{2\omega}^{(2)(\text{CSHG})}$ is independent of the initial phase ϕ_x .

Unlike the PGE, for SHG, both $\sigma_{(2)\text{Re}}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, \omega)$ and $\sigma_{(2)\text{Im}}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, \omega)$ contribute to $\langle j_{\eta} \rangle_{2\omega}^{(2)(\text{L})}$ and $\langle j_{\eta} \rangle_{2\omega}^{(2)(\text{CSHG})}$.

V. GATETUNABLE SECOND-ORDER NONLINEAR OPTICAL RESPONSES FROM RADIO TO INFRARED REGION IN T_d -WTe₂ MONOLAYER

The six-band model of the T_d -WTe₂ monolayer in Ref. 24 can capture the full reciprocal space distribution of geometric quantities such as Berry curvature, while the four-band model of Refs. 20 and 24 can only describe the region near the gap opening points Q and Q' . The ab initio calculations show that the Berry curvature of the highest valence band actually has a large value at a point far from the gap opening points²⁰, which is a conclusion that the four-band model cannot capture but the six-band model can. In addition, when the frequency of light is appropriately high, more bands will be involved in the interband transitions²⁰, so the six-band model is more accurate than the four-band model. Therefore, considering the above reasons, we use the six-band model instead of the four-band model for the calculation.

The six-band $\vec{k} \cdot \vec{p}$ Hamiltonian of monolayer T_d -WTe₂ with a bandgap of 55 meV is²⁴

$$H_0(\vec{k}) = \begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_1 & v_1^+ & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -v_1^- & \epsilon_2 & v_3^+ & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -v_3^- & \epsilon_3 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \epsilon_1 & v_1^- & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -v_1^+ & \epsilon_2 & v_3^- \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -v_3^+ & \epsilon_3 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (54)$$

where $\epsilon_i = c_{i,0} + c_{i,x} k_x^2 + c_{i,y} k_y^2$ and $v_i^{\pm} = \pm v_{i,x} k_x + i v_{i,y} k_y$ for the i -th orbital. The values of parameters in Eq. (54) are listed in Table III of Ref. 24. The applied out-of-plane electric field E_{\perp} causes the total Hamiltonian to become

$$H(\vec{k}) = H_0(\vec{k}) + H_1(\vec{k}), \quad (55)$$

where²⁴

$$H_1(\vec{k}) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & i\delta_{1,z} & 0 & 0 & i\delta_{1,x} & 0 \\ -i\delta_{1,z} & 0 & i\delta_{3,z} & -i\delta_{1,x} & 0 & i\delta_{3,x} \\ 0 & -i\delta_{3,z} & 0 & 0 & -i\delta_{3,x} & 0 \\ 0 & i\delta_{1,x} & 0 & 0 & -i\delta_{1,z} & 0 \\ -i\delta_{1,x} & 0 & i\delta_{3,x} & i\delta_{1,z} & 0 & -i\delta_{3,z} \\ 0 & -i\delta_{3,x} & 0 & 0 & i\delta_{3,z} & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (56)$$

where $\delta_{i,x}$ and $\delta_{i,z}$ are connected to the electric field induced Rashba and Ising spin-orbit couplings, respectively, and they are both k -independent. We approximately take $\delta_{3,x} = \delta_{3,z} = 0$ because they originate from the third energy band far from the Fermi level²⁴. In addition, since $\delta_{1,z}$ overwhelms $\delta_{1,x}$, one can mainly use $\delta_{1,z}$ to describe the spin-orbit coupling induced by E_{\perp} ²⁴. With the increase of $\delta_{1,z}$, the spin splitting of the energy band increases gradually. By comparing with the splitting magnitude of the conduction bands near the gap-opening point at different electric fields calculated by ab initio in Ref. 20, we can know that the electric fields E_{\perp} of 0.2 V/nm, 0.5 V/nm and 1 V/nm correspond to $(\delta_{1,x}, \delta_{1,z}) =$

FIG. 3. (Color online) (a,b,c) The \vec{k} -space distribution of $I_{\text{BCD,LPGE}}^{xyy}$ for Fermi level (a,b) $\epsilon_F = 0$ eV and (c) $\epsilon_F = 0.095$ eV when the frequency $\nu = 1000$ Hz and $E_{\perp} = 0.2$ V/nm. The difference between (a) and (b) is that the large magnitude of $I_{\text{BCD,LPGE}}^{xyy}$ in the rectangular region near Γ point is discarded in (b). The unit of $I_{\text{BCD,LPGE}}^{xyy}$ is $\text{\AA}^3/\text{eV}$.

(0.01, 0.031) eV, (0.01, 0.05) eV and (0.01, 0.099) eV, respectively.

We take the relaxation time τ as 5 ps, which is obtained from optical measurements³⁶. The temperature is taken as 80 K.

The mirror symmetry \mathcal{M}_y of T_d -WTe₂ monolayer leads to the vanishing of the components with an odd number of y indices in the second-order conductivity tensor^{20,22,24}, which is consistent with our following numerical calculations. Thus, from Eqs. (40) and (41), for T_d -WTe₂ monolayer, the currents of CPGE in y and x direction read

$$\begin{aligned} \langle j_y \rangle_{0\omega}^{(2)(\text{LC})} &= -\langle j_y \rangle_{0\omega}^{(2)(\text{RC})} = \frac{1}{2} \sigma_{(2)\text{Im}}^{yyy}(\omega, -\omega) E_0^2, \\ \langle j_x \rangle_{0\omega}^{(2)(\text{LC})} &= \langle j_x \rangle_{0\omega}^{(2)(\text{RC})} \\ &= \frac{1}{4} \left[\sigma_{(2)\text{Re}}^{xxx}(\omega, -\omega) + \sigma_{(2)\text{Re}}^{xyy}(\omega, -\omega) \right] E_0^2. \end{aligned} \quad (57)$$

Consequently, when the circularly polarized light changes from LC to RC, the DC current in the y -direction will be reversed while the DC current in the x -direction remains in the same direction, which is consistent with the experimental observations in Ref. 20. From Eq. (49), for T_d -WTe₂ monolayer, the currents of CSHG in y direction read

$$\begin{aligned} \langle j_y \rangle_{2\omega}^{(2)(\text{LC})} &= -\langle j_y \rangle_{2\omega}^{(2)(\text{RC})} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \sigma_{(2)\text{eff}}^{xyy}(\omega, \omega) E_0^2 \sin(2\omega t + \varphi_2). \end{aligned} \quad (58)$$

A. LPGE (or DC current of NHE) at 1000 Hz

In experiments, Fermi level ϵ_F and the out-of-plane electric field E_{\perp} caused by the gate voltage can be controlled independently and they have significant influence on nonlinear optical responses and NHE^{7,11,20}.

With the use of the traditional BCD formula obtained from the semi-classical Boltzmann equation, the NHE of monolayer WTe₂ in the case where ϵ_F can be varied and in the case where both E_{\perp} and ϵ_F can be varied were studied theoretically by density functional theory (DFT) in Ref. 19 and Ref. 45, respectively. However, only the BCD contribution is included in Refs. 19 and 45 at low frequency and there is no band gap in the band dispersion in Ref. 45 especially, which may not be proper. We first investigate the important effect of the Fermi level on the LPGE or DC current of NHE at 1000 Hz and then compare the results with those in Ref. 19. We consider the following case: the alternating electric field with a low frequency $\nu = 1000$ Hz (angular frequency $\omega = 2\pi\nu$) is set to be along the y direction^{7,24}, and the symmetry analysis shows that the linear charge current in the transverse direction will disappear at this time¹⁰. $\delta_{1,x}$ and $\delta_{1,z}$ are set to 0.01 eV and 0.031 eV, respectively, which corresponds to $E_{\perp} = 0.2$ V/nm. When the Fermi level is 0 eV, from the numerical results we find that the only non-vanishing LPGE conductivity is $\sigma_{(2)}^{xyy}(\omega, -\omega)$, and it is almost all contributed by the BCD term. The real part of $\sigma_{(2)}^{xyy}(\omega, -\omega)$ is -781 nm \cdot $\mu\text{A}/\text{V}^2$ and the imaginary part can be neglected. The integrand of the BCD conductivity of LPGE in Eq. (25) is given as (see SM³⁴)

$$\begin{aligned}
I_{\text{BCD,LPGE}}^{xyy}(\omega, -\omega) &\equiv \text{Re} \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \left[\sum_{nm} \frac{d^\omega d_{nm}^0}{\hbar} \varepsilon_{mn} \xi_{mn}^x \xi_{nm}^y \partial_{k_y} f_{mn}(\vec{k}) + [(y, \omega) \leftrightarrow (y, -\omega)] \right] \right\} \\
&= -\frac{2}{\hbar} \frac{\Gamma}{\omega^2 + \Gamma^2} \left\{ \sum_{nm} \frac{(\varepsilon_{nm}/\hbar)^2}{(\varepsilon_{nm}/\hbar)^2 + \Gamma^2} \text{Im}(\xi_{mn}^x \xi_{nm}^y) \partial_{k_y} f_n(\vec{k}) \right. \\
&\quad \left. - \sum_{nm} \frac{\Gamma \varepsilon_{mn}/\hbar}{(\varepsilon_{nm}/\hbar)^2 + \Gamma^2} \text{Re}(\xi_{mn}^x \xi_{nm}^y) \partial_{k_y} f_n(\vec{k}) \right\}, \tag{59}
\end{aligned}$$

whose \vec{k} -space distribution is plotted in Fig. 3. $I_{\text{BCD,LPGE}}^{xyy}$ are very large near Γ point, but show antisymmetric with respect to Γ point [shown in Fig. 3(a)]. This gives rise to zero BCD-induced LPGE conductivity after integral over the momentum space. To reflect the contributions from the states which are far away from Γ point to $I_{\text{BCD,LPGE}}^{xyy}$, we remove the region nearby Γ point [which takes a rectangular region near Γ point in Fig. 3(b)], but retain the region just around it in Fig. 3(b). Before we start our discussions on the behavior of $I_{\text{BCD,LPGE}}^{xyy}$ in the momentum space, we have to emphasize that $I_{\text{BCD,LPGE}}^{xyy}$ is generally not the same to the usual Berry curvature dipole, i.e., $\sum_n f_n(\vec{k}) \partial_{k_y} \Omega_n^z$. $I_{\text{BCD,LPGE}}^{xyy}$ is only reduced to the usual Berry curvature dipole at the limit of $\Gamma \ll |\varepsilon_{nm}/\hbar|$ (see Section VI). Thus it loses a clear meaning of Berry curvature dipole, but we can see that the distribution of integrand in momentum space shows positive-negative distributions along an axis, which is analogous to a ‘‘dipole’’ in momentum space. For brevity, we call this as dipole distribution. It can be seen that there are two centers of these dipole distributions [at $(k_x, k_y) = (0, \pm 0.105) \text{ \AA}^{-1}$], which give rise to the main contribution to the BCD-induced LPGE conductivity. These dipole distributions are a subtle consequence of the product of $d^\omega d_{nm}^0 \varepsilon_{mn}$, $\partial_{k_y} f_{mn}$ and $\xi_{mn}^x \xi_{nm}^y$ in Eq. (59). For a comparison, if the Fermi level is set to be 0.095 eV, which corresponds to gap-opening points in the energy band dispersion located at Q and Q' in momentum space [see Figs. 2(a) and 1(d)]. It also displays dipole-distribution features near these gap-opening points Q and Q' [see Fig. 3(c)]. The real part of $\sigma_{(2)}^{xyy}(\omega, -\omega)$ tremendously increases to $8.582 \times 10^4 \text{ nm} \cdot \mu\text{A}/\text{V}^2$ (from $-781 \text{ nm} \cdot \mu\text{A}/\text{V}^2$ for Fermi level at 0 eV), which is mainly contributed by these dipoles and the order of magnitude is consistent with $\sigma_{(2)}^{xyy}(\omega, -\omega)$ estimated in Ref. 19⁴⁶. Furthermore, when $E_\perp = 0.2 \text{ V/nm}$ and $\nu = 1000 \text{ Hz}$, the dependence of the LPGE or DC current of NHE on the Fermi level can be found in Fig. 4(a), and its trend and order of magnitude are qualitatively consistent with Ref. 19 (see Fig. 2(b) of Ref. 19).

B. LPGE and CPGE at higher frequencies

Now we turn to the case of higher frequencies. For LPGE with the alternating electric field along the y direction, from Eq. (39) we know that only $\text{Re}(\sigma_{(2)}^{xyy}(\omega, -\omega))$

and $\text{Re}(\sigma_{(2)}^{yyyy}(\omega, -\omega))$ need to be calculated. For CPGE, from Eq. (42) we know that only $\text{Im}(\sigma_{(2)}^{xxy}(\omega, -\omega))$ and $\text{Im}(\sigma_{(2)}^{yxy}(\omega, -\omega))$ need to be calculated. We first calculated the LPGE and CPGE conductivities with a large range of frequencies and Fermi levels, and the results show that in the range of 10^3 Hz - 10^{13} Hz , $\text{Re}(\sigma_{(2)}^{yyyy}(\omega, -\omega))$ and $\text{Im}(\sigma_{(2)}^{xxy}(\omega, -\omega))$ vanish while $\text{Re}(\sigma_{(2)}^{xyy}(\omega, -\omega))$ and $\text{Im}(\sigma_{(2)}^{yxy}(\omega, -\omega))$ are present, as well as they are almost all contributed by the $\text{Re}(\sigma_{(2)\text{BCD}}^{xyy}(\omega, -\omega))$ and $\text{Im}(\sigma_{(2)\text{BCD}}^{yxy}(\omega, -\omega))$, respectively. The frequency ν and Fermi level ε_F dependence of $\text{Re}(\sigma_{(2)\text{BCD}}^{xyy}(\omega, -\omega))$ and $\text{Im}(\sigma_{(2)\text{BCD}}^{yxy}(\omega, -\omega))$ for $E_\perp = 0.2 \text{ V/nm}$ are shown in Fig. 4 and our calculations also find the same trend as Fig. 4 when E_\perp increases to 0.5 V/nm and 1 V/nm, except that the value of conductivities increases. From the aspect of Fermi level, the maximum value of PGE conductivities occurs when the Fermi level is equal to 0.095 eV and -0.11 eV , which correspond to the vicinity of the gap-opening points in the band dispersion [see Fig. 2(a)]. The value and sign of the PGE conductivities can be changed greatly when changing the Fermi level through the gate voltage, which may be useful for fabricating electrically switchable rectifiers²⁷. From the aspect of frequency, in the radio region (about less than 10^9 Hz), the LPGE varies very little with frequency and the CPGE disappears. When ν is greater than 10^9 Hz , the LPGE conductivity and the CPGE conductivity start to gradually decrease and increase, respectively, with increasing frequency. Thus, we next take a careful look at LPGE and CPGE in the region of 5 GHz-500 GHz, which covers a large part of the microwave region (0.3 GHz-300 GHz). Figs. 5(a)-(c) show the rapid decrease of $\text{Re}(\sigma_{(2)\text{BCD}}^{xyy}(\omega, -\omega))$ as the frequency increases from 5 GHz to 100 GHz. The frequency dependence of the LPGE and CPGE in Figs. 4 and 5 can be directly explained by $\text{Re}(\sigma_{(2)\text{BCD}}^{xyy}(\omega, -\omega)) \propto 1/(\omega^2 + \Gamma^2)$ and $\text{Im}(\sigma_{(2)\text{BCD}}^{yxy}(\omega, -\omega)) \propto \omega/(\omega^2 + \Gamma^2)$, respectively, which can be known from Eqs. (59) and (60). Among Figs. 5(d)-5(f), the maximum CPGE response with a value of $7.14 \times 10^4 \text{ nm} \cdot \mu\text{A}/\text{V}^2$ occurs when $\nu = 30 \text{ GHz}$, $\varepsilon_F = 0.08 \text{ eV}$ and $E_\perp = 1 \text{ V/nm}$.

FIG. 4. (Color online) (a,b) The frequency ν and Fermi level ε_F dependence of (a) LPGE conductivity $\text{Re}(\sigma_{(2)BCD}^{xyy}(\omega, -\omega))$ and (b) CPGE conductivity $\text{Im}(\sigma_{(2)BCD}^{xyy}(\omega, -\omega))$ for $E_{\perp} = 0.2 \text{ V/nm}$. Here, the frequencies are taken as $10^3, 10^4, 10^5, \dots, 10^{13} \text{ Hz}$. The Fermi level range is from -0.25 eV to 0.15 eV with an interval of 0.005 eV . The relaxation time is taken as 5 ps .

Many nonlinear optics experiments are measured in the infrared region of light (0.3 THz - 400 THz)^{20,37,47,48}. When the frequency ν is greater than 400 THz , the corresponding photon energy is greater than 1.65 eV . As can be seen from the band dispersion calculated by DFT in Fig. 1(e) of Ref. 20, more bands will be involved in the interband transitions at this time, and our six-band model may be inaccurate. Therefore, we next choose the frequency range 5 THz - 400 THz to investigate the dependence of LPGE and CPGE

on Fermi level and frequency under different E_{\perp} . For LPGE with alternating electric field along the y -direction, the non-vanishing conductivity is $\text{Re}(\sigma_{(2)}^{xyy}(\omega, -\omega))$, which is almost all contributed by the IB3 term. As shown in Figs. 6(a)-6(c), $\text{Re}(\sigma_{(2)IB3}^{xyy}(\omega, -\omega))$ has relatively large values of about $500 \text{ nm} \cdot \mu\text{A}/\text{V}^2$ to $1000 \text{ nm} \cdot \mu\text{A}/\text{V}^2$ in the range of 50 THz - 100 THz . For CPGE, $\text{Im}(\sigma_{(2)}^{xyy}(\omega, -\omega))$ disappears while $\text{Im}(\sigma_{(2)}^{yxxy}(\omega, -\omega))$ is present. $\text{Im}(\sigma_{(2)}^{xyy}(\omega, -\omega))$ is mainly contributed by the IB2 term and the contributions from the BCD and IB3 terms are smaller than that from the IB2 term by an order of 10^3 . Among Figs. 6(d)-6(f), the maximum CPGE response with a value of $5.07 \times 10^5 \text{ nm} \cdot \mu\text{A}/\text{V}^2$ occurs when $\nu = 90 \text{ THz}$, $\varepsilon_F = 0.07 \text{ eV}$ and $E_{\perp} = 0.5 \text{ V/nm}$. In a word, the ν , ε_F and E_{\perp} dependence of PGE are complicated in the infrared region.

It can be known directly from Eq. (S64) of SM³⁴ that our theory of the independent particle approximation only considers transitions connecting identical \vec{k} points⁴⁹. Therefore, we plot the energy difference $\Delta\varepsilon(k_x, k_y)$ between the lowest conduction band and the highest valence band (see Fig. S1 of SM³⁴) and find that the minimum of $\Delta\varepsilon(k_x, k_y)$ is located near the gap-opening points. When $E_{\perp} = 0.2 \text{ V/nm}$, 0.5 V/nm and 1 V/nm , the minimum values of $\Delta\varepsilon(k_x, k_y)$ are 0.233 eV , 0.2065 eV and 0.133 eV respectively (consistent with previous calculations in Ref. 20), which correspond to the required frequencies of 56.34 THz , 49.93 THz and 32.16 THz for the interband transitions. In the infrared region, large values of PGE exist only when the frequency is greater than 50 THz (see Fig. 6), which implies a possible connection between the IB2, IB3 terms and the interband transitions.

C. LSHG (or Second harmonic current of NHE) and CSHG

For LSHG with the alternating electric field along the y -direction, from Eq. (51) we know that only $\sigma_{(2)\text{eff}}^{xyy}(\omega, \omega)$ and $\sigma_{(2)\text{eff}}^{yyy}(\omega, \omega)$ need to be calculated. For CSHG, from Eq. (53) we know that only $\sigma_{(2)\text{eff}}^{xxy}(\omega, \omega)$ and $\sigma_{(2)\text{eff}}^{yxy}(\omega, \omega)$ need to be calculated. We first calculated the effective LSHG and CSHG conductivities with a large range of frequencies and Fermi levels by using Eqs. (23), (51) and (53), and the results show that in the range of 10^3 Hz - 10^{13} Hz , $\sigma_{(2)\text{eff}}^{yyy}(\omega, \omega)$ and $\sigma_{(2)\text{eff}}^{xxy}(\omega, \omega)$ vanish while $\sigma_{(2)\text{eff}}^{xyy}(\omega, \omega)$ and $\sigma_{(2)\text{eff}}^{yxy}(\omega, \omega)$ are present, as well as they are almost all contributed by the real and imaginary parts of the BCD term when ν is less than 10^{12} Hz . The frequency ν and Fermi level ε_F dependence of $\sigma_{(2)\text{eff}}^{xyy}(\omega, \omega)$ and $\sigma_{(2)\text{eff}}^{yxy}(\omega, \omega)$ for $E_{\perp} = 0.2 \text{ V/nm}$ are shown in Fig. 7 and our calculations also find the same trend as Fig. 7 when E_{\perp} increases to 0.5 V/nm and 1 V/nm , except that the value of conductivities increases. Surprisingly, the ν and ε_F dependence of CSHG and LSHG have almost the same trend and values by comparing Fig. 7(a) and Fig. 7(b). From the aspect of Fermi level, the two large peaks of SHG conductivities occur when the Fermi level is equal to the energy corresponding

FIG. 5. (Color online) (a,b,c) The frequency ν and Fermi level ε_F dependence of LPGE conductivity $\text{Re}(\sigma_{(2)\text{BCD}}^{xyy}(\omega, -\omega))$ for (a) $E_{\perp} = 0.2$ V/nm, (b) $E_{\perp} = 0.5$ V/nm and (c) $E_{\perp} = 1$ V/nm. (d,e,f) The frequency ν and Fermi level ε_F dependence of CPGE conductivity $\text{Im}(\sigma_{(2)\text{BCD}}^{yxy}(\omega, -\omega))$ for (d) $E_{\perp} = 0.2$ V/nm, (e) $E_{\perp} = 0.5$ V/nm and (f) $E_{\perp} = 1$ V/nm. Here, the frequency range for numerical calculations is from 5 GHz to 500 GHz with an interval of 5 GHz. The Fermi level range is from -0.25 eV to 0.15 eV with an interval of 0.005 eV. The relaxation time is taken as 5 ps.

to the vicinity of the gap-opening points in the band dispersion. From the aspect of frequency, in the radio region (about less than 10^9 Hz), the SHG conductivities are almost constant with increasing frequency. When ν is greater than 10^9 Hz, the SHG conductivities start to gradually decrease with increasing frequency.

Next we turn to the infrared region (0.3 THz- 400 THz, i.e., 0.3×10^{12} Hz- 400×10^{12} Hz). It remains that $\sigma_{(2)\text{eff}}^{yyy}(\omega, \omega)$ and $\sigma_{(2)\text{eff}}^{xxy}(\omega, \omega)$ vanish while $\sigma_{(2)\text{eff}}^{xyy}(\omega, \omega)$ and $\sigma_{(2)\text{eff}}^{yxy}(\omega, \omega)$ exist. As shown in Fig. 8, the ν , ε_F and E_{\perp} dependence of the SHG are complicated and there are contributions of about the same order of magnitude from the BCD and IB3 terms. The SHG conductivities have relatively large values in the range of 5 THz- 125 THz. Comparing Figs. 6(d)-(f) and Figs. 8(d)-(f), we can know from Eqs. (57) and (58) that in the frequency range of 125 THz- 300 THz and in the y -direction, the CSHG almost disappears and only a large CPGE exists,

which is a very special property that may be attractive for circularly polarized infrared photodetection^{25,26} and electromagnetic wave energy harvesting rectifiers²⁷ without the disturbance of CSHG.

D. The case of relaxation time of 10 fs

Relaxation times of 10 fs have also been measured in some experimental samples^{7,12,20,37}. Therefore we next investigate the case of $\tau = 10$ fs. In the range of 10^3 Hz- 10^{14} Hz, for LPGE, only $\text{Re}(\sigma_{(2)}^{xyy}(\omega, -\omega))$ exists, which is mainly contributed by the BCD term. The ν and ε_F dependence of $\text{Re}(\sigma_{(2)\text{BCD}}^{xyy}(\omega, -\omega))$ is also similar to Fig. 4(a) (see Fig. 9). Compared to the case of $\tau = 5$ ps, the difference is that the order of magnitude of $\text{Re}(\sigma_{(2)\text{BCD}}^{xyy}(\omega, -\omega))$ decreases by

FIG. 6. (Color online) (a,b,c) The frequency ν and Fermi level ε_F dependence of LPGE conductivity $\text{Re}(\sigma_{(2)IB3}^{xyy}(\omega, -\omega))$ for (a) $E_{\perp} = 0.2$ V/nm, (b) $E_{\perp} = 0.5$ V/nm and (c) $E_{\perp} = 1$ V/nm. (d,e,f) The frequency ν and Fermi level ε_F dependence of CPGE conductivity $\text{Im}(\sigma_{(2)IB2}^{yxy}(\omega, -\omega))$ for (d) $E_{\perp} = 0.2$ V/nm, (e) $E_{\perp} = 0.5$ V/nm and (f) $E_{\perp} = 1$ V/nm. Here, the frequency range for numerical calculations is from 5 THz to 400 THz with an interval of 5 THz. The Fermi level range is from -0.25 eV to 0.15 eV with an interval of 0.005 eV. The relaxation time is taken as 5 ps.

a factor of 1000, and from the viewpoint of frequency, the LPGE photocurrent only begins to decrease gradually when the ν is greater than 10^{12} Hz. For CPGE, we find that there is almost no CPGE photocurrent when ν is less than 10^{13} Hz. As shown in Fig. 10, in the region of 5 THz-400 THz [it covers a large part of the infrared region (0.3 THz-400 THz)], the LPGE current still exists in the range of 5 THz-100 THz, which is mainly contributed by the BCD term. For CPGE, BCD, IB2, and IB3 terms all have about the same order of magnitude contribution to the total conductivity, so the situation becomes more complicated than the case of $\tau = 5$ ps.

The CPGE in the WTe₂ monolayer at $\varepsilon_F \approx 0$ eV, $\tau = 10$ fs, $\nu = 29$ THz and different E_{\perp} has been investigated experimentally and theoretically in Ref. 20. Our theoretical results for $\text{Im}(\sigma_{(2)}^{yxy}(\omega, -\omega))$ in Fig. 10(e) are consistent in the order of magnitude with the experimentally measured approximate value $177 \text{ nm} \cdot \mu\text{A}/\text{V}^{220}$ when $E_{\perp} = 0.5$ V/nm.

VI. DISCUSSION

In the frequency range we considered above, the wavelength of the applied light is much larger than the characteristic size of the system^{1,50,51}, the wave vector of the photon is small and the photon drag effect^{1,3} can be ignored. The experimental scheme for **measuring nonlinear optical conductivities from radio to infrared region is illustrated in the SM³⁴ and the schematic illustration of photocurrents that need to be measured in order to verify our theory in T_d -WTe₂ monolayer is shown in Fig. 11.**

In the clean limit, for the PGE, the BCD term exists only under circularly polarized light¹⁴ because the BCD term is purely imaginary [see Eq. (18)]. However, Figs. 4(a) and 9 show that the BCD term in the case of considering scattering effects has a real part and it contributes significantly to the LPGE, which shows the necessity of considering a finite Γ in the calculation of second-order nonlinear optical responses.

Next we discuss the difference between the BCD formula Eq. (25) obtained by the quantum kinetics and the traditional

BCD formula obtained by the semi-classical Boltzmann equation. According to Eq. (25), the integrand of the BCD conductivity of CPGE is given as (see SM³⁴)

$$\begin{aligned}
I_{\text{BCD,CPGE}}^{yx}(\omega, -\omega) &\equiv \text{Im} \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \left[\sum_{nm} \frac{d^\omega}{\hbar} \frac{d_{nm}^0}{\hbar} \varepsilon_{mn} \xi_{mn}^y \xi_{nm}^y \partial_{k_x} f_{mn}(\vec{k}) + \sum_{nm} \frac{d^{-\omega}}{\hbar} \frac{d_{nm}^0}{\hbar} \varepsilon_{mn} \xi_{mn}^y \xi_{nm}^x \partial_{k_y} f_{mn}(\vec{k}) \right] \right\} \\
&= \frac{1}{\hbar} \frac{\omega}{\omega^2 + \Gamma^2} \left\{ \sum_{nm} \frac{(\varepsilon_{nm}/\hbar)^2}{(\varepsilon_{nm}/\hbar)^2 + \Gamma^2} \text{Im} (\xi_{mn}^y \xi_{nm}^x) \partial_{k_y} f_n(\vec{k}) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \sum_{nm} \frac{\Gamma \varepsilon_{mn}/\hbar}{(\varepsilon_{nm}/\hbar)^2 + \Gamma^2} \left[\xi_{mn}^y \xi_{nm}^y \partial_{k_x} f_n(\vec{k}) - \text{Re} (\xi_{mn}^y \xi_{nm}^x) \partial_{k_y} f_n(\vec{k}) \right] \right\}. \tag{60}
\end{aligned}$$

For LPGE (CPGE), considering that the system has time-reversal symmetry, the contribution of the second line of Eq. (59) [Eq. (60)] to the conductivity can be easily shown to be equal to 0 and we only need to consider the first line of Eq. (59) [Eq. (60)]. Only when $\Gamma \ll |\varepsilon_{nm}/\hbar|$, Eqs. (59) and (60) can be reduced to the form of the Berry curvature dipole $\sum_n f_n(\vec{k}) \partial_{k_y} \Omega_n^z$. Therefore, from Eqs. (59) and (60) we can see that the BCD term Eq. (25) is so complicated that it loses the meaning of ‘‘Berry curvature dipole’’ of the traditional BCD formula. From the aspect of PGE conductivities, when $\Gamma \ll |\varepsilon_{nm}/\hbar|$, using Eq. (18), Eq. (25) reduces to

$$\begin{aligned}
\sigma_{(2)\text{BCD}}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, -\omega) &\approx -\frac{e^3}{2\hbar^2} \frac{i}{\omega + i\Gamma} \int \frac{d^3k}{(2\pi)^3} \sum_n \Omega_n^{\eta\beta} \partial_{k_\alpha} f_n(\vec{k}) \\
&\quad - \frac{e^3}{2\hbar^2} \frac{i}{-\omega + i\Gamma} \int \frac{d^3k}{(2\pi)^3} \sum_n \Omega_n^{\eta\alpha} \partial_{k_\beta} f_n(\vec{k}). \tag{61}
\end{aligned}$$

For LPGE,

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{Re} \left(\sigma_{(2)\text{BCD}}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, -\omega) \right) &\approx \frac{e^3}{2\hbar^2} \frac{\Gamma}{\omega^2 + \Gamma^2} \int \frac{d^3k}{(2\pi)^3} \sum_n f_n(\vec{k}) (\partial_{k_\alpha} \Omega_n^{\eta\beta} + \partial_{k_\beta} \Omega_n^{\eta\alpha}), \tag{62}
\end{aligned}$$

which is consistent with Eq. (5) of Ref. 25 when $\eta\alpha\beta = xyy$ or yyx ⁵². For CPGE,

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{Im} \left(\sigma_{(2)\text{BCD}}^{\eta\alpha\beta}(\omega, -\omega) \right) &\approx \frac{e^3}{2\hbar^2} \frac{\omega}{\omega^2 + \Gamma^2} \int \frac{d^3k}{(2\pi)^3} \sum_n f_n(\vec{k}) (\partial_{k_\alpha} \Omega_n^{\eta\beta} - \partial_{k_\beta} \Omega_n^{\eta\alpha}). \tag{63}
\end{aligned}$$

Moreover, we can use numerical results to illustrate the difference between the BCD formula Eq. (25) and the traditional BCD formula. At $\tau = 5$ ps, $\nu = 1000$ Hz, $\varepsilon_F = 0.095$ eV, $E_\perp = 0.2$ V/nm, for the NHE or LPGE, using the formulas in Refs. 10, 19, and 25 or Eq. (62), we can obtain the traditional Berry curvature dipole and its resulting conductivity $\sigma_{(2)\text{BCD}}^{xyy}(\omega, -\omega)$ of 0.464 Å and 4.290×10^4 nm · $\mu\text{A}/V^2$,

respectively. This conductivity result is very close to the result of 4.291×10^4 nm · $\mu\text{A}/V^2$ calculated by Eq. (25)⁵². In the SM³⁴, we explain why the results of the two BCD formulas are very close at $\tau = 5$ ps, $\varepsilon_F = 0.095$ eV, $E_\perp = 0.2$ V/nm and the frequency range of 1000 Hz-1 THz. Hence at this time we can safely use the traditional BCD formula to approximately calculate the LPGE or the DC current of NHE. However, considering the premise of Eq. (18), we set $\tau = 10$ fs, $\nu = 1000$ Hz, $\varepsilon_F = 0.08$ eV and $E_\perp = 1$ V/nm. At this time the traditional Berry curvature dipole and its resulting conductivity are 1.58 Å and 292.15 nm · $\mu\text{A}/V^2$, respectively. This conductivity result has a large difference of 39.95 nm · $\mu\text{A}/V^2$ compared to the result of 252.2 nm · $\mu\text{A}/V^2$ calculated by Eq. (25). In addition, we also find that the IB3 term at this time has a contribution of 16.95 nm · $\mu\text{A}/V^2$. Therefore, it is more accurate to use Eqs. (23)-(27) to calculate the NHE or second-order nonlinear optical responses for some materials with complex energy band structures and femtosecond-scale relaxation times.

In this work, we used the length-gauge approach to describe the interaction between the electron and the alternating electric field³³, while the velocity-gauge approach was used in Refs. 4 and 33. The results obtained from the length gauge and the velocity gauge have been shown to be equivalent³³. The advantage of length gauge is that conductivities from different terms can be closely linked to insulators or metals²⁸ so that the physics is transparent and neat.

Some discussion on relaxation time can be seen in the SM³⁴. Various scattering processes could lead to additional current generation mechanisms⁵³⁻⁵⁶ and the effect of these scattering details beyond the relaxation time approximation on the nonlinear optical responses of WTe₂ monolayer deserves future exploration. Besides, we do not consider the electron-electron interaction and its resulting exciton effect in the present work. However, both theories and experiments show that the exciton effect has a significant impact on the optical response of 2D materials^{50,57,58}. How to accurately and completely include the complex exciton effect on PGE and SHG in the quantum kinetics method still deserves further study.

The quantum kinetic method can also be extended for the

FIG. 7. (Color online) (a,b) The frequency ν and Fermi level ϵ_F dependence of (a) LSHG conductivity $\sigma_{(2)\text{eff}}^{xyy}(\omega, \omega)$ and (b) CSHG conductivity $\sigma_{(2)\text{eff}}^{yyy}(\omega, \omega)$ for $E_{\perp} = 0.2 \text{ V/nm}$. Here, the frequencies are taken as $10^3, 10^4, 10^5, \dots, 10^{13} \text{ Hz}$. The Fermi level range is from -0.25 eV to 0.15 eV with an interval of 0.01 eV . The relaxation time is taken as 5 ps .

study of transport phenomena under magnetic fields. For example, in Ref. 59, the anomalous planar Hall effect caused by applying an in-plane magnetic field in a 2D heavy-hole system was found to be a purely intrinsic phenomenon, and this novel effect can serve as an ingenious scheme to unambiguously probe the effect of Berry curvature on transport; Bhalla *et al.*⁶⁰ proposed that applying linearly polarized light on the surface of a doped topological insulator with in-plane magnetization would lead to a second-order DC current with resonant feature, and this new effect is called resonant photovoltaic effect. The influence of applying a magnetic field or performing exchange bias on the nonlinear optical responses of WTe_2 monolayer remains a subject of future study. In addition, a quantum kinetic theory for the nonlinear response of ballistic topological edge states has been developed⁶¹, so the nonlinear optical response of the helical edge states of the quantum spin Hall insulator WTe_2 monolayer in various frequency regions is also worthy of future exploration.

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FIG. 8. (Color online) (a,b,c) The frequency ν and Fermi level ε_F dependence of LSHG conductivity $\sigma_{(2)\text{eff}}^{xyy}(\omega, \omega)$ for (a) $E_{\perp} = 0.2$ V/nm, (b) $E_{\perp} = 0.5$ V/nm and (c) $E_{\perp} = 1$ V/nm. (d,e,f) The frequency ν and Fermi level ε_F dependence of CSHG conductivity $\sigma_{(2)\text{eff}}^{yxy}(\omega, \omega)$ for (d) $E_{\perp} = 0.2$ V/nm, (e) $E_{\perp} = 0.5$ V/nm and (f) $E_{\perp} = 1$ V/nm. Here, the frequency range for numerical calculations is from 5 THz to 400 THz with an interval of 5 THz. The Fermi level range is from -0.25 eV to 0.15 eV with an interval of 0.01 eV. The relaxation time is taken as 5 ps.

FIG. 9. (Color online) (a,b,c) The frequency ν and Fermi level ε_F dependence of LPGE conductivity $\text{Re}(\sigma_{(2)\text{BCD}}^{xyy}(\omega, -\omega))$ for (a) $E_{\perp} = 0.2$ V/nm, (b) $E_{\perp} = 0.5$ V/nm and (c) $E_{\perp} = 1$ V/nm. Here, the frequencies are taken as $10^3, 10^4, 10^5, \dots, 10^{14}$ Hz. The Fermi level range is from -0.25 eV to 0.15 eV with an interval of 0.01 eV. The relaxation time is taken as 10 fs.

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FIG. 10. (Color online) (a,b,c) The frequency ν and Fermi level ε_F dependence of LPGE conductivity $\text{Re}(\sigma_{(2)}^{xy}(\omega, -\omega))$ for (a) $E_{\perp} = 0.2 \text{ V/nm}$, (b) $E_{\perp} = 0.5 \text{ V/nm}$ and (c) $E_{\perp} = 1 \text{ V/nm}$. (d,e,f) The frequency ν and Fermi level ε_F dependence of CPGE conductivity $\text{Im}(\sigma_{(2)}^{xy}(\omega, -\omega))$ for (d) $E_{\perp} = 0.2 \text{ V/nm}$, (e) $E_{\perp} = 0.5 \text{ V/nm}$ and (f) $E_{\perp} = 1 \text{ V/nm}$. Here, the frequency range is from 5 THz to 400 THz with an interval of 5 THz. The Fermi level range is from -0.25 eV to 0.15 eV with an interval of 0.01 eV . The relaxation time is taken as 10 fs.

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FIG. 11. (Color online) (a,b) Schematic illustration of photocurrents that need to be measured in order to verify our theory in $T_d - \text{WTe}_2$ monolayer. (a) LPGE and LSHG. A monochromatic linearly polarized light with electric field vector along the y -axis incident along the normal to $T_d - \text{WTe}_2$ monolayer with $z = 0$ in the xy plane. Due to the mirror symmetry \mathcal{M}_y , the second-order currents in the y -direction disappear and only second-order DC and second harmonic currents exist in the x -direction. The second-order currents in the x -direction are induced by the non-zero $\text{Re}(\sigma_{(2)}^{xyy}(\omega, -\omega))$ and $\sigma_{(2)\text{eff}}^{xyy}(\omega, \omega)$. (b) CPGE and CSHG. A monochromatic circularly polarized light incident along the normal to $T_d - \text{WTe}_2$ monolayer with $z = 0$ in the xy plane. From Eqs. (57) and (58), we know that DC and second harmonic currents exist in both x and y directions under circularly polarized light. However, due to the mirror symmetry \mathcal{M}_y , when the circularly polarized light changes from LC to RC, the DC and second harmonic currents in y direction will be reversed while the DC and second harmonic currents in x direction keeps the same magnitude and direction. Thus the CPGE and CSHG responses [see Eqs. (42) and (52)] exist only in the y direction, which are induced by the non-zero $\text{Im}(\sigma_{(2)}^{yxy}(\omega, -\omega))$ and $\sigma_{(2)\text{eff}}^{yxy}(\omega, \omega)$.

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